

KASR TARTIBLI DIFFERENSIAL TENGLAMALAR UCHUN IKKINCHI TARTIBLI RUNGE-KUTTA METODI

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Annotation: In this article, we use the second order Runge–Kutta method to solve fractional differential equations and their systems with the initial conditions. And we cover calculations of its values using the algorithms in the Python programming language. Solution is established to the different values of α which is the order of fractional differential equation.

Keywords: Caputo fractional differential derivative and integral, the second order Runge–Kutta method.

Annotatsiya: Ushbu maqolada biz kasr tartibli differensial tenglamalar va ularning sistemasi uchun boshlang'ich shartli masalalarni yechishni Runge-Kutta usulidan foydalanganmiz. Hamda uning qiymatini hisoblash uchun Python dasturlash tilidagi algoritmdan foydalangan holda hisoblashni yoritib berganmiz. Yechim hosila tartibi α ning turli qiymatlari uchun chizilgan.

Kalit so'zlar: Kaputo kasr tartibli hosila va integral, ikkinchi tartibli Runge-Kutta metodi.

Hozirgi vaqtda kasr tartibli integral va hosilalar nazariyasi funksiyalar nazariyasining tarmoqlaridan biri bo'lib, muhim amaliy ahamiyatga ega bo'lmoqda [1-6]. Kasr tartibli hosila va integrallarga asoslangan matematik modellashtirish, turli jarayonlar va hodisalar o'zgarishini baholashda, matematik biologiyada [7], gidrogeologiyada issiqlik va massa almashinish jarayonlarini bir xil bo'lmagan muhitda modellashtirishda [8-10], transonik oqimlarning elastoplastiklik muammolari, yarimo'tkazgichlar sohasidagi tadqiqotlar, epidemiologiyada, moliya va boshqa yo'nalishlarda e'tirof etiladi.

Kasr tartibli integrallar va hosilalar o'ziga xos xususiyatlarga ega va kasr integrallari va hosilalari bilan tenglamalarni yechishning analitik usullari har doim ham samarali emas. Shu bois ko'p hollarda biz sonli usullarga mjdurojat qilmoqdamiz. So'nggi yillarda sonli usullar keng rivojlandi. Biroq, ushbu yo'nalishda erishilgan muvaffaqiyatlarga qaramay, shunga o'xshash muammolarning umumiy sinfi uchun taqribiy usullardan foydalanishni nazariy asoslash masalasi ochiqligicha qolmoqda.

Aytaylik $\alpha > 0$ va $n = \alpha$ bo'lsin. Kaputo α kasr tartibli hosila quyidagicha ta'riflanadi:

$${}^C D_t^\alpha f(t) = \frac{1}{\Gamma(n-\alpha)} \int_a^t (t-u)^{n-\alpha-1} \left(\frac{d}{du}\right)^n f(u) du$$

$a=0$ uchun, quyidagicha belgilash kiritamiz:

$${}^C D_t^\alpha f(t) = D^\alpha f(t).$$

Endi Ikkinchi tartibli Runge-Kutta metodi (RK2) kasr tartibli differensial tenglamani taqribiy yechishning birinchi Eyley metodining kengaytmasidir.

$$D^\alpha y(t) = f(t, y(t)), \quad y(t_0) = y_0, \quad 0 < \alpha \leq 1$$

bu yerda $y \in C^{p+1}([t_0, t_0 + T])$.

Bu holatda yechim quyidagi diskret ko'rinishda qidiriladi:

$$y_{n+1} = y_n + \frac{h^\alpha}{\Gamma(\alpha+1)} \frac{K_1 + K_2}{2},$$

bu yerda

$$K_1 = f(t_n, y_n),$$

$$K_2 = f\left(t_n + \frac{h^\alpha}{\Gamma(\alpha+1)}, y_n + \frac{h^\alpha}{\Gamma(\alpha+1)} K_1\right),$$

Isbot. Belgilash kiritamiz

$$K_1 = f(t_n, y_n),$$

$$K_2 = f\left(t_n + A \frac{h^\alpha}{\Gamma(\alpha+1)}, y_n + B \frac{h^\alpha}{\Gamma(\alpha+1)} K_1\right),$$

bu yerda A va B ikkita haqiqiy noma'lum o'zgarmlar.

Taylor qatoriga yoyilmaning lokal xatoligi

$$E(h) = y_{n+1} - y_n$$

$$y_{n+1} = y(t_n + h), \quad t_{n+1} = t_n + h, \quad y_n = y(t_n).$$

Ravshanki, xatolikni minimallashtirish uchun biz quyidagi shartlarni inobatga olishimiz shart:

$$E(0) = D^\alpha E(0) = \dots = D^{p\alpha} E(0) = 0, \quad D^{(p+1)\alpha} E(0) \neq 0.$$

Taylor ko'phadidan foydalangan holda quyidagiga ega bo'lamiz:

$$E(h) = y_{n+1} - y_n = \frac{h^\alpha}{\Gamma(\alpha+1)} D^\alpha y_n + \frac{h^{2\alpha}}{\Gamma(2\alpha+1)} D^{2\alpha} y_n + O(h^{3\alpha}) = \frac{h^\alpha}{\Gamma(\alpha+1)} f(t_n, y_n) + \frac{h^{2\alpha}}{\Gamma(2\alpha+1)} D^{2\alpha} y_n + O(h^{3\alpha})$$

$$D^\alpha E(h) = f(t_n, y_n) + \frac{h^\alpha}{\Gamma(\alpha+1)} D^\alpha y_n + O(h^{2\alpha})$$

va

$$y_{n+1} - y_n = C_1 \frac{h^\alpha}{\Gamma(\alpha+1)} K_1 + C_2 \frac{h^\alpha}{\Gamma(\alpha+1)} K_2.$$

Shunga ko'ra, natijada $E[h]$ va $D^\alpha E[h]$:

$$E[h] = C_1 \frac{h^\alpha}{\Gamma(\alpha+1)} K_1 + C_2 \frac{h^\alpha}{\Gamma(\alpha+1)} K_2,$$

$$D^\alpha E[h] = c_1 K_1 + c_2 K_2 + \frac{h^\alpha}{\Gamma(\alpha+1)} D^\alpha K_2,$$

$$D^\alpha K_2 = D^\alpha f \left(t_n + A \frac{h^\alpha}{\Gamma(\alpha+1)}, y_n + B \frac{h^\alpha}{\Gamma(\alpha+1)} K_1 \right),$$

$$D^\alpha K_2 = D^\alpha f \left(t_n + A \frac{h^\alpha}{\Gamma(\alpha+1)}, y_n + B \frac{h^\alpha}{\Gamma(\alpha+1)} K_1 \right) = f_{t_n + A \frac{h^\alpha}{\Gamma(\alpha+1)}} A + f_{y_n + B \frac{h^\alpha}{\Gamma(\alpha+1)} K_1} B K_1$$

$h \rightarrow 0$ uchun:

$$D^\alpha E[0] = C_1 K_1[0] + C_2 K_2[0],$$

$$f(t_n, y_n) = C_1 f(t_n, y_n) + C_2 f(t_n, y_n) \quad \Rightarrow \quad 1 = C_1 + C_2,$$

$$D^{2\alpha} E(h) = D^\alpha (D^\alpha E(h)) = C_2 D^\alpha K_2 + D^\alpha K_2.$$

$D^{2\alpha} E(0) = D^{2\alpha} y_n(t)$ dan tashqari va:

$$D^{2\alpha} y(t) = D^\alpha (f(t, y(t))) = f_t + f_y D^\alpha y(t) = f_t + f f_y.$$

Natija:

$$2C_2 A f_{t_n}(t_n, y_n) + 2C_2 B f_{y_n}(t_n, y_n) f_{y_n}(t_n, y_n) = f_{y_n}(t_n, y_n) + f(t_n, y_n) f_{y_n}(t_n, y_n)$$

Vanihoyat, quyudagi sitemasiga erishamiz:

$$\begin{cases} C_1 + C_2 = 1 \\ 2C_2 A - 1 = 0 \\ 2C_2 B - 1 = 0 \end{cases}$$

$C_1 = C_2 = \frac{1}{2}$ uchun $\frac{h^\alpha}{\Gamma(\alpha+1)}$ qadam bilan klassik RK2 metodiga ega bo'lamiz.

Misol. Kasr tartibli differensial tenglamani RK2 metodi bilan yeching.

$$D^{\frac{1}{2}} y(t) = t^2 + \frac{y^2}{4}, \quad y(0) = 1.$$

Python dasturlash tilida yechimni hisoblash uchun algoritm quramiz:

```
import numpy as np
import math
import matplotlib.pyplot as plt
```

```
from scipy.special import gamma, factorial
h=0.2
a=0.5
d=math.pow(h,a)/gamma(a+1)
k1=[]
k2=[]
t=np.arange(0,1.1,h)
y=[1]*len(t)
def f(t, y):
    return t*t+y**2/4
for i in range (len(t)-1):
    k1.append(f(t[i],y[i]))
    k2.append(f(t[i]+d,y[i]+d*k1[i]))
    y[i+1]=y[i]+d*(k1[i]+k2[i])/2
plt.plot(t,y,'r^--')
plt.show
y
01,
0.2    1.2073270850154547,
0.4    1.5602938303746137,
0.6    2.200113447200271,
0.8    3.468996502039549,
16.5976489485722025
```


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